

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT SPEECH THROUGH CONCEPTS RELATED TO LANGUAGE PHENOMENA IN LINGUISTICS

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In the speech of students, it is advisable to provide feedback based on the science of logic. Therefore, they move the reserve of words in their memory through their speech. The concept of speech and its cultivation. Speech is the use of thinking based on the type of activity of a person, the means of language (word, vocabulary, sentence). Speech serves as a function of interaction and message, to express and influence mutual thought with emotion. Well-developed speech serves as one of the most important means of active activity of a person in society. And for the student, speech is a weapon of successful education in school.

Today's Uzbek it can be said that linguistic terms can fully express concepts related to language phenomena. It can be said that a dictionary of terms representing concepts used at all language levels has been created. These include synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, paronyms, phrases, idioms, etymological dictionary, spelling dictionary, dictionary of direct linguistic terms. However, some dictionaries, textbooks, and manuals also show differences in the use of linguistic terms. This situation is especially noticeable in school textbooks and higher education textbooks.

For example, instead of a term, it is possible to observe cases such as term, synonym-synonym, antonym-opposite, homonym-synonym, phonetic-soundology, lexicology-wordology. But it should not be forgotten that it is not enough to translate or replace one or two terms. Of course, it is necessary to take into account the fate of the creations related to that changed term. For example, if we replace the term homonym with a formative term, how do we call such terms as homonymy, homophone, homograph, omolexeme.

At the beginning of the last century, the need for pedagogical terms increased as a result of the growth of the national consciousness of the Turkestan people, the reform of schools and madrasas, and the wider teaching of worldly knowledge in them. New Muslim schools of Behbudi, Shakuri, Ainiy, Hamza, Munavar Qori, Avloni and others opened in Russia, Crimea, Orenburg, got acquainted with their teaching and teaching methods and started opening schools adapting them to local conditions. As a result, textbooks and manuals suitable for these schools appeared, and special terms related to education began to be formed in these textbooks for the first time.

In addition to these, there are also a lot of borrowed terms that express pedagogical concepts. Institute, pedagogy, method, practice, applicant, school, lesson, teacher, exam, book, school, etc.

I. Ismailov's monograph published in 1966 is considered one of the important works. It is important that in this case, "blood kinship terms" in Uzbek and Uyghur languages (father, mother, brother, uncle, aunt, grandfather, grandmother, aunt, granddaughter), "kinship terms that appeared after marriage" (husband, wife, son-in-law, daughter-in-law, pochcha, boja, ovsin, father-in-law, mother-in-law, god-in-law), finally, one of the "names of closeness expressed by the word tutingan" (tutingan father, tutingan mother, tutingan son, tutingan sister, tutingan brothers) differences from each other, similarities, appearance of such terms and norms of practical use are thoroughly analyzed. As the author himself notes, "the difference between the Uzbek and Uyghur terms of kinship, as well as their historical development and appearance in dialects, is discussed. The general unity of these languages and the specific characteristics of each language and their differences from each other are analyzed." As an important evidence, we would like to emphasize that in the following years, several more works dedicated to the comparative study of some lexical layers of Turkic languages appeared. One of them is called "Development of the lexicon of the Turkic languages of Central Asia and Kazakhstan".

References

1. N. Uluqov Tilshunoslik nazariyasi. O 'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'рта maxsus ta'lim vazirligi tomonidan universitetlarning 5120100 -filologiya va tillarni o'qitish (o'zbek filologiyasi) bakalavriat ta'lim yo'nalishi 1-kursialabarlari uchun o'quv qo'llanma Toshkent –2016.
2. Tibbiy terminlar lug'ati Hammabop Tibbiyot Qo'llanmasi 2013. 765-bet
3. Madvaliyev A. O'zbek tilida kimyo terminlari va ularning izohli lug'atda berilishi. O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. 2008-yil, 5-son.

